

EU, Transnational and International Law Series

EUTILS

Quaderni di diritto UE, transnazionale e internazionale

Études de droit de l'UE, transnational et international

Forschung im EU, transnationalen und internationalen Recht

*Cuadernos de derecho de la Unión europea, derecho transnacional y
internacional*

The EUTILS Project: a European multicentric, multilingual, open-science, not-for profit, scientific-publishing project

Dialogue of legal traditions and cultures

The EU, Transnational and International Law Series (EUTILS) project is conceived as a multicentric, multilingual, open science, not for profit, scientific-publishing project, committed to publishing original scientific research in the fields of EU Law, Transnational Law and International Law, following highest scientific standards of peer-reviewed legal literature.

The EUTILS project is based on the shared assumption that EU, transnational and international legal literature, besides the always growing English speaking dimension, continues to develop important contributions in other linguistic traditions, too.

Access to all such traditions, and dialogue between them, is an important condition to develop a truly “European” approach to legal thinking - and, besides that, a truly transnational one.

It does not seem, however, that truly multilingual publishing frameworks have so far developed, where monographic studies, and academic edited books can be published, under the strictest guarantees of scientific quality, and following an open science approach.

The EUTILS project wants to fill that gap, and is therefore meant to be open - at least - to monographic / edited book contributions in EU, Transnational and International Law written in one of the languages representing the **most relevant and influential cultural traditions of legal studies** concerning the EU integration, transnational legal phenomena including private international law, international law and international organisations law.

The **5 working languages of the EUTILS project** will therefore be, from its very beginning, besides English, Italian, French, German and Spanish. As a goal, this will also be reflected by the working languages of the members of EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board.

Other working languages might be added, essentially according to the composition of the Scientific Editorial Board, and following a decision by that Board and advice by the Scientific Advisory Board.

The relevant fields

The EUTILS project will lead to the publication of **EUTILS Series**, as better articulated below, having as their possible objects scholarly monographs, and edited books dedicated to legal studies in the fields of EU law, including its relationship with the laws of its Member States, its “autonomous” influence on such laws, as well as on the laws of third countries (candidate countries, associated countries, or else), and its external dimension; transnational law, including private international law and arbitration; international law, in its various fields, including international organisations law.

Multilingualism

Multilingualism, and the dialogue between different scholarly/linguistic traditions will be at the basis of the EUTILS Series publishing policies.

Monographs will have to be drafted in one of the EUTILS working languages, and will be accompanied by a substantial résumé in at least a different EUTILS working language.

Edited books will contain contributions mainly drafted in one of the EUTILS working languages, but can also include contributions in other European languages.

Open-Science and multicentric - An accessible, sustainable and non-elitist publishing model

Open-science, and not-for profit publishing will be the second core element of the EUTILS Series publishing policies, striving to build a multicentric, Europe-wide publishing framework.

The EUTILS project starts at the initiative of the University of Padova, one of the oldest Universities in Europe (<https://www.unipd.it/en/university-padua>) whose raison d'être has always been, and still is, that of being a beacon of freedom of research and to promote the exchange of ideas among different cultures in Europe (and, later, throughout the world).

In line with this tradition, the EUTILS project is not meant to be a “one actor” initiative, but is conceived as a multicentric, open network of like-minded academics and research-groups, active throughout Europe, and willing to value their research through an open-science, and accessible framework.

PUP -> multicentrism

To this end, the EUTILS project can count on the support of the Padova University in-house publishing structure, Padova University Press (PUP), which is willing to offer its collaboration on a not-for-profit basis, and following an extremely flexible, open-science approach.

The books will carry the PUP impressum and logo.

However, given the multicentric nature of the EURILS project, upon a decision by the EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board, a EUTILS book can simultaneously also carry the logo of another university / university department / research center having funded the relevant research / publication.

This will in particular be the case for “dedicated” sub-series, which might be published under a Series’ title directly referring to a participating research institution / scholarly association (see the details below).

Open access e-books / printed runs

As a basis, EUTILS monographs and edited books will be published as **open access e-books**, having an **ISBN code** linked to the PUP catalogue.

At the same time they will be uploaded on **Zenodo**, a publicly funded European open science repository (<https://about.zenodo.org/>), operating inside the **OpenAIRE** open scientific repository European concept.

Thanks to this configuration, it will be possible for all participants to the EUTILS project to directly link the Zenodo-EUTILS platform (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eutils>), and the individual monographs / edited books appearing therein, using their respective academic research webpages/portals.

The not-for-profit approach granted by PUP, linked to the e-book basis for publication, will ensure the viability of very low budget initiatives, the only decisive criterion for publication being then not funding availability, but scientific quality of the proposed publications.

Moreover, while the use of a public open-science platform will ensure the widest possible access to EUTILS publications, its multilingualism policies (better defined below) will try to ensure enhanced accessibility to works drafted in different languages.

This being the base-line, **printed runs of the books** will be also possible - with **adjustable volume**, based on the choices taken during the editorial process, in agreement with the author/editor of each publication, on the basis of the budget available for each publication.

Why this publishing model?

Essentially, because we are convinced that science is a **public good**, and research should, as far as possible, be framed as accessible and socially sustainable social endeavour.

We are convinced that good science is not necessarily science that originates from “big money”. This is particularly true in the field of social sciences, where the “lab” is, essentially, a virtual one, made up by the open exchange of ideas among researchers and research groups.

Moreover, we think that **sustainability of public funded research**, as well as a **non-elitist, inclusive and equitable** understanding of research, make a “no-frills / no-market” approach to high quality publishing one of the wisest possible choices.

The EUTILS Series II Detailed editorial approach

Legal studies + interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary studies in the relevant fields

The EUTILS project foresees a scalable approach, featuring several possible “Series”, each with specific publishing policies, inside a general, common framework.

Studies accepted for publication will have to fall into the relevant fields as indicated above. They will have to be predominantly legal in their scope, but might also include interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary studies having a clear relevance for the legal thought.

A clear link between the proposal and the proponent’s expertise

Authors shall justify their proposal, showing its connection with their expertise in the field. This will be done in different ways according to the level of seniority of the proponent author. In principle, the relevant statement / recommendation should at least refer to the academic position of the proponent author / supervisor / mentor in a field relevant for the proposed monograph. Failing that, it should clearly explain the link existing between the proposed monograph and an ongoing / past research project involving qualified experts in the relevant field, detailing the members of the relevant research group, their scientific qualifications, and their roles and responsibilities in the research project, with special reference to those of the proponent and of the experts having supervised her/his activities in that research project.

Should such a reasonable link fail to appear, the Scientific Editorial Board will reject the proposal.

Proposals to be inserted in dedicated sections of a Series, devoted to scientific output originating from a specific research institution / scholarly association will follow specially agreed proposal-paths reaching the same quality-oriented guarantee.

A scalable editorial approach

The EUTILS Series will have a basic architecture, articulated in two macro-sectors (Legal Monographs and Edited Books).

Special sections / dedicated sub Series might be developed, to highlight specific areas of research / the origin of the research in specific research institutions / scholarly associations.

In particular, the EUTILS project is meant to be open not only to developing specialised series (on areas such as, e.g.: competition law; cultural property law; environment and climate change law; human rights law; international arbitration; international courts; migrations; peace studies; private international law, ...), but is also meant to favor the development of a “multicentric” open science publishing approach. By that, we mean an approach involving the creation of dedicated sub Series devoted to scientific output originating from a specific research institution / scholarly association.

Should that possibility be considered of interest to a research institution / scholarly association, specific arrangements would have to be agreed, to ensure that the overall philosophy of the EUTILS project, and the specificities of the relevant research institution / scholarly association, are safeguarded.

The basic architecture

The basic architecture of the EUTILS Series will lie in the following articulation.

1. Legal Monographs

a. Legal Monographs Series

A **Legal Monographs Series - LMS** will be open to publishing monographic works by established scholars and scholars that have already obtained their PhD.

The assessment procedure will be different according to different seniority levels.

If the proponent/author is a **postdoc scholar with at least 8 years of experience since PhD completion, and holds a tenured position in a recognized university / research institute**, the Scientific Editorial Board will examine reasoned proposals coming directly from the proponent/author.

If the proponent/author is a **postdoc scholar with 2-7 years of experience since PhD completion**, having conducted postdoc research under the supervision of a postdoc mentor who's an expert of the relevant field and holds a tenured position in a recognized university / research institute, the proposal should be accompanied by an **endorsement of the mentor/supervisor**.

If the proponent/author is a **postdoc scholar with less than 2 years of experience since PhD completion**, the EUTILS Monograph Series will be open to publishing their PhD monographic work, developed under the supervision of an expert of the relevant field, and **recommended for publication by the relevant PhD body** (PhD council, PhD defence board) of a recognized university / research center. In such case, the Scientific Editorial Board will examine reasoned proposals coming from the PhD supervisor / joint PhD supervisors, accompanied by the statement of recommendation for publication issued by the relevant PhD body.

If the proponent/author **doesn't fit into the precedent categories**, nor holds a tenured position in a recognized university / research center since at least 2 years, the proposal should be accompanied by a **letter of recommendation issued by a recognized expert** of the subject matter, holding a tenured position in a recognized university / research center since at least 2 years, explaining the link between her/him, her/his research group(s), and the proponent/author's research.

The Scientific Editorial Board can either decide to start the peer review process, or reject the proposal (desk rejection).

If it decides to start the peer review process, the Scientific Editorial Board will submit the proposed monograph for **peer review to two anonymous, blind reviewers**.

If the Board deems it necessary, it may request the assessment of a third reviewer (anonymous, double blind).

Based on the reviewers assessment, the Scientific Editorial Board will take the final decision on the publication.

The proposed monograph will have to be drafted in **one of the EUTILS working languages**.

If accepted, it will have to be accompanied by a **substantial résumé in at least a different EUTILS working language**, as well as **standard abstracts** (1 page/400 words) and keywords in **all other EUTILS working languages**.

2. Edited Books Series

An **Edited Books Series - EBS** will be open to publishing **collections of contributions** (scholarly articles), brought together thematically, and **accompanied by a substantial scholarly introduction**.

Proposals for edited books can be put forward by scholars holding a research position, tenured or non tenured (other than PhD student), in a recognized university / research center.

An edited book can in particular contain :

- a. a collection of solicited original articles on a particular theme;
- b. a combination of original *and* previously published articles on a particular theme;
- c. a collection of previously published articles. Such collections will in principle include contributions that are not part of a previous unitary volume, but could also be translations of contributions that appeared in an earlier volume, in one or more EUTILS working languages other than the one in which they were originally published.

The EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board will examine **reasoned proposals** submitted by the interested scholar (book editor), explaining the research ideas, the scientific methodology/ies followed, and the selection policy that informed the choice of the contributions.

The Scientific Editorial Board can either decide to start the peer review process, or reject the proposal (desk rejection).

The **peer review assessment** can be unitary, in that the Scientific Editorial Board might decide to submit the edited book proposal, as a whole, to a double review. In such a case, one review will be carried by an anonymous and blind reviewer, the other being conferred to one of the Scientific Editorial Board members. Editors / contributors who happen to be members of the Scientific Editorial Board will not be entrusted with such tasks.

Alternatively, the Scientific Editorial Board might deem appropriate to approve the Edited Book project “as such”, but will then submit each contribution to an anonymous and blind reviewer, and exclude contributions not having passed the review process.

The **contributions** to the proposed **edited book** will have to be mainly drafted in one of the **EUTILS working languages**. They will have to be accompanied by short abstracts in at least two other EUTILS working languages, already at the submission stage.

Original contributions in other European languages - spoken by at least one member of the Scientific Editorial Board - can also be included in an edited book submission predominantly featuring EUTILS working languages. They will have to be accompanied, already at the submission stage, by a substantial résumé in one of the EUTILS working languages, as well as short abstracts in at least two other EUTILS working languages.

If accepted, contributions will have to be accompanied by standard abstracts (1 page/400 words) and keywords in all EUTILS project working languages.

3. Working Paper Series

A **Working Paper Series - WPS** will be open to anticipating the publication, via Zenodo, of works that might later appear in either the Legal Monographs Series or in the Edited Book Series.

Pending peer review, proposals submitted to the General Editor for inclusion in the LMS or EBS might be included in the WPS as accepted publications with embargo.

They will be rendered public after completion of the peer review process, so that their content will be available to the scientific community before the completion of the editorial process by PUP and final publication in the LMS or EBS.

III. Publication Policies

Ethics

The EUTILS project is committed to maintaining the highest level of integrity. It adheres to the core principles of publication ethics as articulated by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) (see <https://publicationethics.org/>).

We encourage the best standards of publication ethics and take all possible measures against publication malpractices.

A detailed Publication Ethics and Publication Malpractice Statement of the EUTILS project is made available through the EUTILS platform/EUTILS Zenodo Community

Boards

The EUTILS project will be managed through a Scientific Editorial Board, acting in connection with a Scientific Advisory Board.

Scientific Editorial Board

The members of the EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board are recognized experts in the field of European, Transnational and International Law. They are members of or affiliated with universities and research institutes from across Europe.

The EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board is coordinated by the General Editor. General Editor is Prof. Bernardo Cortese, Full Professor of EU Law at the University of Padova.

The Scientific Editorial Board and the General Editor may be supported by a group of Managing Editors.

The Scientific Editorial Board meets on the initiative of the General Editor. The meetings can be in presence, on-line, hybrid. The Scientific Editorial Board can also work on distance, through email exchanges.

The Scientific Editorial Board can meet either in a full session, or in groups.

It will meet in full session for important editorial policy decisions. If it meets in a full session all members need to be invited to join such a session, and at least one third of their institutions need to be represented in the session.

Scientific Advisory Board

The EUTILS Scientific Advisory Board includes recognized experts in the field of European, Transnational and International Law. They are current or previous judges of EU and international courts, members or *emeriti* of renowned universities and research institutes active in the fields of interest of the EUTILS project, or recognized practitioners in such fields.

Advisory Board members are in principle not involved in the decision-making process of the EUTILS Series and are only acting as external advisors.

As a whole, the Advisory Board provides a forum for advice and feedback on the general strategic editorial choices and initiatives linked with the EUTILS Series, as well as a pool of possible double-blind peer-reviewers for book proposals.

Scientific Advisory Board members' advice is given on an individual basis.

EUTILS Publication Ethics and Publication Malpractice Statement

The EUTILS project is committed to maintaining the highest level of integrity. It adheres to the core principles of publication ethics as articulated by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) (see <https://publicationethics.org/>).

We encourage the best standards of publication ethics and take all possible measures against publication malpractices.

Anyone who believes that these guidelines have not been followed should raise their concern with the General Editor or upload a notice on the EUTLS Platform/website.

Duties and responsibilities of editors and reviewers

Confidentiality

The editors will not disclose any information about a submitted article to anyone other than the author, other members of the EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board, the managing editors, reviewers, potential reviewers, other editorial advisers, and the publisher.

Peer review process

All content published in EUTILS Series is subject to a peer review process.

Publication proposals can be submitted by authors through the means indicated on the EUTILS platform/EUTILS Zenodo Community.

After submitting their proposal, authors receive a confirmation that the proposal has been received and are informed as soon as possible as to whether the article will be submitted to peer-review.

The proposal is examined by the EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board, which can decide to reject it (desk rejection) if it does not fall within the scope of the EUTILS project as a whole, or of its existing Series, if it does not comply with the editorial guidelines, if it does not comply with EUTILS Series authorship / originality requirements, if it is under review elsewhere, or if it appears prima facie to fall short of acceptable standards of research quality.

Publication proposals intended for the Legal Monographs Series or the Edited Book Series are subject to a double-blind peer review process. Publication in the Working Paper Series is not subject to peer review.

EUTILS peer review is conducted by at least two referees. One referee is always external to the Scientific Editorial Board. At least one of the referees is “blind”.

Specific Series reviewing policies apply.

Upon accepting the assignment, the referee will assess the author's contribution within a period of 1 month.

The referee's assessment will be based on the assessment form approved by the Scientific Editorial Board, which the referee will submit via the EUTILS platform/EUTILS Zenodo Community/PUP reviewing platform.

The publication proposal may be accepted, considered acceptable with minor or major revisions, after revision and resubmission, or rejected.

If the referees suggest to ‘revise and resubmit’ the article, the article is subject to new assessment after the resubmission.

The main criterion for acceptance is whether the contribution is of good/excellent quality with regard to the state of knowledge in the field.

Disclosure and conflict of interest

Conflict of interest exists when an editor has financial or personal relationships that inappropriately influence (bias) his or her actions.

Such relationships are also known as dual commitments, competing interests, or competing loyalties.

Editors who make final decisions about manuscripts have no personal, professional, or financial involvement in any of the issues they might judge.

Should editors submit their own manuscripts for consideration, the EUTILS Series shall ensure that they are not involved in the decision-making and review process, and all information regarding their manuscripts is kept confidential.

All participants in the peer-review and publication process must disclose all relationships that could be viewed as potential conflicts of interest.

Editors require all contributors to disclose relevant competing interests and publish corrections if competing interests are revealed after publication.

Editors will not use unpublished information disclosed in a submitted article for their own research purposes without the author's explicit written consent.

Privileged information or ideas obtained by editors as a result of handling the article will be kept confidential and not used for their personal advantage.

Publication decisions

The General Editor is responsible for deciding which of the submitted proposals will be published, based on the validation of the publication proposal by the Scientific Editorial Board, its importance to researchers and readers, its quality with regard to the state of knowledge in the relevant field, the reviewers' comments, and such legal requirements as are currently in force regarding libel, copyright infringement and plagiarism.

The General Editor cannot override a negative advice by the Scientific Editorial Board, but it can ask it to reconsider it in a full session.

Procedures for dealing with unethical behaviour

Editors (in conjunction with the publisher) will take responsive measures when ethical concerns are raised with regard to a submitted article or published paper.

Every reported act of unethical publishing behaviour will be looked into, even if it is discovered years after publication.

The author should be given the opportunity to respond to any allegations.

If, on investigation, the ethical concern is well-founded, a correction, retraction, expression of concern or another note as may be relevant, will be published in the EUTILS Platform.

Duties and responsibilities of reviewers

Confidentiality

All articles received for review are confidential documents and must be treated as such; they must not be shown to or discussed with others except if authorized by the managing editor

(who would only do so under exceptional and specific circumstances). This applies also to invited reviewers who decline the review invitation.

Conflict of interest

Conflict of interest exists when a reviewer has financial or personal relationships that inappropriately influence (bias) his or her actions. Such relationships are also known as dual commitments, competing interests, or competing loyalties.

Any invited referee who has conflicts of interest should immediately notify the editors to declare their conflicts of interest and decline the invitation to review.

Promptness

Any invited referee who feels unqualified to review the article or knows that its prompt review will be impossible should notify the managing editor and decline the invitation to review.

Acknowledgements of sources

Reviewers should notify the editors of any substantial similarity or overlap between the article under consideration and any other manuscript (published or unpublished) known to them.

Duties and responsibilities of authors

Authorship

Monographs can be sole authored or co-authored. If co-authored, authors will have to carefully explain their respective roles and responsibilities.

Authors should justify to the Scientific Editorial Board the link between their scientific activities and the field in which they propose to publish. This can be done via the PhD supervisor / postdoc mentor recommendation, if applicable, and via a personal statement of the proponent. That statement, as well as the PhD supervisor / postdoc mentor recommendation, should at least refer to the academic position of the proponent / supervisor / mentor in a field relevant for the proposed monograph, or, failing that, to the link existing between the proposed monograph and an ongoing / past research project involving qualified experts in the relevant field, detailing the members of the relevant research group, their scientific qualifications, and their roles and responsibilities in the research project, with special reference to those of the proponent and of the experts having supervised her/his activities in that research project.

Conflict of interest

Conflict of interest exists when an author (or the author's institution) has financial or personal relationships that inappropriately influence (bias) his or her actions. Such relationships are also known as dual commitments, competing interests, or competing loyalties.

When authors submit a manuscript, whether an article or another publication, they are responsible for disclosing all financial and personal relationships that might bias their work. Examples of potential conflicts of interest which should be disclosed include employment, consultancies, stock ownership, honoraria, paid expert testimony, patent applications/registrations, and grants or other funding. Potential conflicts of interest should be disclosed at the earliest stage possible. Readers should be informed about who has funded research and on the role of the funders in the research.

Submitting the same manuscript to more than one publisher, or even to more than one publication at the same publisher, without full disclosure is not deemed acceptable.

Plagiarism

Authors should ensure that they only submit entirely original works, and if they have used the work and/or words of others, that this has been appropriately cited. EUTILS does not tolerate plagiarism in any form (including self-plagiarism) and reserves the right to check all submissions through appropriate plagiarism checking tools. Submissions containing suspected plagiarism will be rejected.

Research fraud

The Serie is committed to combat research fraud and preserve research integrity. Especially when it comes to empirical research, research fraud refers to publications that report results and draw conclusions from data that are not generated by the study (fabrication) or are generated by manipulating the data (falsification).

Duties and responsibilities of the publisher

Handling of unethical publishing behaviour

In cases of alleged or proven scientific misconduct, fraudulent publication or plagiarism, the publisher, in close collaboration with the editors, will take all appropriate measures. This includes the prompt publication of an erratum, clarification or, in the most severe case, the retraction of the affected work. The publisher, together with the editors, shall take reasonable steps to identify and prevent the publication of papers where research misconduct has occurred, and under no circumstances encourage such misconduct or knowingly allow such misconduct to take place.

Access to Series content

The EUTILS project is committed to the permanent availability and preservation of scholarly research and ensures accessibility by partnering with organizations and maintaining a digital archive. In particular, one or several Zenodo communities will be created to permanently store the published books, and to make the peer reviewing process transparent.

The Zenodo pdf file will also be accessible through a link at the Padova University Press (PUP) catalogue / website, free of charge.

It might also be linked via another university / research center platform.

Padova University Press: ISBN, impressum and logo

Padova University Press (PUP) will provide the ISBN to the EUTILS project books. The books will carry the Padova University Press impressum and logo.

Upon a decision by the EUTILS Scientific Editorial Board, a EUTILS book can simultaneously carry the logo of another university /research center having funded the research / publication.

The logo will appear in an appropriate area of the published product.